

Speculation on Quantum Wavelength Relationship to Classical Density Scenarios

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We have tried to argue in previous notes that the origin of a quantum free particle wavelength is linked with the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ through the process of establishing E and px as independent terms which leave A unchanged. Given that x, t transforms as a 4-vector, one must introduce $dt = \text{constant}/E$ and $dx = \text{constant}/p$ to accomplish this. In other notes, we have considered features such as $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) / \sqrt{L}\sqrt{L} = 1/L = \text{classical spatial density}$, and $\exp(ipx)$ being a probability in x which ensures conservation of momentum etc. We have also tried to link these various scenarios together.

Here, we consider the role of probability densities appearing in classical physics and argue that if one is logically consistent, then this consistency leads to an $\exp(ipx)$ being associated with a momentum p even though one might at first argue that p is proportional to an impulse hit and requires no associated $\exp(ipx)$ function. In particular, we begin with the classical notion of a spatial density of a free particle as being proportional to dt as given in (1), i.e. $P(x)dx = C dx/|v(x)| = dx/L$. Even though dt is used in this approach, the normalization process implies that $1/L$ holds for different velocities and momenta. This density is not one which distinguishes between different v and rest mass values which yield the same p or different p values for that matter.

If one only considers p (momentum) as proportional to impulse one might argue that there is no need for an associated spatial density. Newtonian mechanics certainly does not assign one. Given, however, that p does not distinguish between $m_1v_1 = m_2v_2$ and neither does $P(x) = dx/L$, we argue that one must at least associate $1/L$ with p to be consistent. At this point, this seems like a purely formal association with almost no practical consequences. If one, however, considers classical statistical mechanics for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, then elastic time reversal balanced scattering $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ yield the MB distribution. The point we make is that $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ follows from Newtonian mechanics and does not require any notion of probability. $f(e_i)$, however, incorporates this energy conservation law as: $\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$.

If a probability (linked with collisions) is directly connected with energy conservation in two body scattering, then given that p is proportional to an impulse hit which is part of momentum conservation, there should be a probability which yields momentum conservation as well. Otherwise there is logical inconsistency. There is already a $1/L$ spatial probability density associated with any p , but this is not linked to momentum conservation. Thus, there should be another probability density which has nothing to do with $f(p)$ (i.e. how many particles have p as there is only one). It seems that one must seek a $P(p, x)$ which ensures momentum conservation, but is still tied with $1/L$ which, from classical considerations because there is no reason to have two independent probabilities with only one leading to p -conservation.. We argue that these ideas lead to $\exp(ipx)$ as a candidate.

We also note that the spatial Shannon's entropy linked with $1/L$, like $1/L$ itself, loses information about the wavelength for the infinite well potential. For consistency, it seems that in the quantum case, one must introduce a second, wavelength related entropy, just as there is a second probability $W(x)$ (wavefunction) associated with $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$

Classical Spatial Probability Density of a Bound Particle

In (1), a classical spatial probability density is introduced as being proportional to $dt(x)$, i.e. the amount of time a particle spends in each constant dx unit:

$$P(x)dx = C dx / |v(x)| \quad \text{where } \frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2 + V(x) = E \quad (\text{nonrelativistic case}) \quad ((1))$$

For a constant $v(x)$, $P(x)dx = dx/L$, ((2)) where L is an arbitrary length.

One may note that in this approach, one calculates relative probabilities and then uses a normalization constant so that $\int P(x)dx = 1$. As a result, all different constant v and p values have the same relative weight and also the same $P(x)$. This probabilistic approach does not distinguish between any of them.

The Case of Impulse Proportional to Momentum

If one considers a constant momentum p , it is proportional to impulse (if $p \rightarrow -p$). One might argue that there is no reason whatsoever to associate a spatial probability density with p . One may further note that $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ yield the same impulse hit and so one is not really interested in the speed of the particle. The same impulse hit occurs for v_1 and v_2 . This lack of distinguishing power is consistent with $P(x) = 1/L$ and so for this reason alone we argue that one must associate, at least formally, $1/L$ with p . One may, however, argue that such an association has almost no practical consequences, although one may devise scenarios for which it shows that one may have an impulse hit at any x with the same probability. We argue, however, that the idea of linking p with a spatial probability is very important as it will ultimately force one to use this probability or a related one to enforce p -conservation.

Classical Conservation Laws and Classical Statistical Densities

An interesting example of a conservation law (energy) being manifested through a probability appears in the Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((2b))$$

Taking \ln of ((2b)) and linking with $-1/T$ multiplied by ((2a)) yields $\exp(-e_i/T) C$. We stress that $f(e_i)$ carries the information of conservation of energy. In other words, if one measured $f(e_i)$ experimentally and used ((2b)) on the basis of the argument that a collision occurs if a particle is present, one would be able to deduce ((2a)), i.e. conservation of energy. Thus, a conservation law may be carried within a probability and its interaction description ((2b)).

One may notice that if one only has two particles which collide elastically, there would be no notion of $f(e_i)$. $f(e_i)$ only appears in an equilibrium picture of many particles as $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is actually linked with many particles. If one adopts the Newtonian viewpoint of no probability linked with a single particle with constant p , then there is no quantum $\exp(ipx)$. The problem, we argue, is that (1) has associated a $P(x)=1/L$ with a particle with momentum p and so one may argue that if a quantity e is conserved and has an associated probability which enforces this conservation, it is logically inconsistent for p to have an associated probability which does not enforce p -conservation.

The Case of Momentum Again

We have argued above that a constant momentum p must have an associated spatial density $1/L$, even though this does not seem to influence the actual impulse and does not distinguish between different constant p or v values. Impulse hits, however, occur in two body scattering which is governed by conservation of momentum. If two body scattering gives rise to an e -probability which governs e -conservation, then if p is associated with a probability, by logical consistency, this probability should also give rise to conservation of p . This, however, is unusual because for a single p one would normally not associate any probability. (1), however, gives a spatial probability $1/L$ and so a probability must exist. $1/L$, however, does not yield conservation of momentum. This seems to lead to two scenarios. One is to argue that it is fine to have $P(x)=1/L$, but that there is no other probability which yields p -conservation. This, however, is logically inconsistent with the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. The second scenario is to try to introduce a second probability which yields conservation of momentum, but at the same time is consistent with $P(x)=1/L$, so that one does not have two completely independent probabilities. It does not seem to make sense to have a $P(x)$ and a $P_1(p,x)$ being completely independent and only one being linked to p -conservation. This approach goes beyond Newtonian mechanics which does not consider any $P_1(p,x)$ associated with a particle with constant p . We also note that one does not need to know the v of the particles, it is only p which is important due to the impulse hit. This seems to be quite different from the Newtonian approach of focusing on $x=vt$. Thus:

$$\text{Function } (P_1(p,x)) = 1/L \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad P_1(p_1,x) P_1(p_2,x) = P_1(p_3,x) P_1(p_4,x) \quad ((3b))$$

For ((3b)), we use the Maxwell-Boltzmann AND probability approach and like this classical statistical case, a constant to the power of p (in 1 dimension here) is a solution. If one considers p and $-p$ for p_1 and p_2 , overall momentum is 0. This is mathematically consistent with $P(x)=1/L$ which is a uniform distribution. As we have noted previously, a 1 power p multiplied by a 1 power $-p$ yields a constant which could be $1/L$ if one uses $1/\sqrt{L}$ as a normalization. The problem, however, becomes creating the full p conservation with a power $-p$ as one does not obtain 0 for non- p -conservation cases. To obtain this required 0, one may use the periodic function $\exp(ipx)$ which still uses p as the exponent. Then:

$$\int dx \quad P_1^*(p_3,x) P_1^*(p_4,x) P_1(p_1,x) P_1(p_2,x) = 0 \quad \text{if } p_1+p_2 \neq p_3+p_4 \quad ((4))$$

In other words, associating a $P_1(p,x)$ with p implies one must consider probability in space in order to introduce p -conservation, something which does not happen in Newtonian mechanics because there is no probability associated with p and one enforces p -conservation as a rule at a point. We suggest that on the grounds of logical consistency, the presence of classical probability which both exists and enforces e conservation means that if one insists on a classical probability $P(x) = 1/L$, linked with every p , then this must somehow be linked with a $P_1(p,x)$ which enforces p -conservation.

Independence of t and x

In the above treatment of $P(x)=1/L$ and $P_1(p,x)$, we explicitly decouple t and x , i.e. do not use $x=vt$, because neither $P(x)=1/L$ nor a $P_1(p,x)$ which enforces conservation of momentum require following a particle in time and space. Conservation of momentum may be thought of as occurring in space by itself (or in time independently). Even $P(x)=1/L$ cannot distinguish between any p and v values because it is based on relative probabilities and a normalization constant. It is thus classically that one sees an independence of t and x , but only if one introduces probabilities. In Newtonian mechanics, there is no probability for dynamics and $x=vt$ is key in analysis.

One may note that special relativity is consistent with Newtonian mechanics, i.e. Newtonian results appear in the $v \ll c$ limit. Special relativity should also be based on dynamics, i.e. $x=vt$ for a particle with constant v . Given that x,t transforms as a 4-vector in special relativity, one may obtain Lorentz invariant expressions which contain both t and x , such as $A = -Et+px$ (one dimension). If one considers a t independent of x scenario, one must introduce the notion of probability based on the above discussion. X and t are linked with the Newtonian viewpoint, i.e. $x(t)$, but one may make $-Et$ and px independent and still keep A constant through:

$$dt = \text{constant}/E \text{ and } dx = \text{constant}/p \quad ((5))$$

This, however, must be linked with a probability, but it is if one considers a distribution in time with a base $.5 dt$ and an independent one in space, with a base $.5 dx$. We have discussed in previous notes that this is again consistent with $\exp(ipx)$.

Shannon's Entropy

Shannon's entropy is given by $-\sum_i f_i \ln(f_i)$. The classical probability $P(x)=1/L$ leads to:

$$-\int dx \frac{1}{L} \ln(1/L) = \ln(L) \quad ((6))$$

$((6))$ is only concerned with the length L as $1/L$ holds for any p or v . $((6))$ is the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy linked with length. If one has $\exp(ipx)$, then as argued above, this stands on its own as a probability and distinguishes between different p values given that each $.5 \hbar/p$ region (for a free particle) has its own distribution. As we have noted previously, if there are two different probabilities $P(x)=1/L$ and $P_1(p,x)=\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$, one may argue for

two different Shannon's entropies. In the $\exp(ipx)$, one may try to describe the randomness over different base lengths \hbar/p , thus even $\ln(L) = \ln(.5 \hbar/p)$ would yield a second entropy which distinguishes between p values.

Conclusion

Although we have discussed approaches of finding the quantum free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, through various probabilistic arguments in previous notes, here we focus on establishing a logical consistency between approaches used in classical physics. In particular, we point out two considerations. The first is that one may associate a spatial probability $P(x)dx = Cdx/|v(x)| = dx/L$ with a free particle, bound in L , as argued in (1). In Newtonian mechanics, this is not done as one focuses on $x(t)$. As a result, a constant p should be associated with $1/L$ and one may note that this spatial probability does distinguish between p or v values. Associating $1/L$ with p , at first, seems to be formal (and possibly leads to almost no practical consequences).

The second classical probability consideration is that of the Maxwell-Boltzmann case for which $\exp(-e_i/T)$ actually encodes conservation of energy if one considers $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$. This equation is based on a collision occurring if a particle is present. Such an argument should apply to conservation of momentum as well. If one only has two particles, then there is no MB $f(e)$ or $f(p)$, but if (1) suggests that p is associated with $1/L$, then one might argue, based on logical consistency, for a $P_1(p,x)$ which yields p -conservation and is directly linked with $1/L$. (One does not want two independent x related probabilities.) We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ is the complex math probability which achieves this. We also suggest that if there is a Shannon's entropy linked with $P(x)=1/L$, there should also be one associated with $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ which quantifies the \hbar/p length region and its associated probability.

References

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